

tillers were converted to 0-9 damage scales.

Of the 907 entries tested, 7.5% were rated resistant (scores 0, 1, and 3) on hill basis and 8.8% on tiller basis (Table 1).

More entries were rated as resistant on tiller basis than on hill basis. This non-correspondence was marked in some varieties (Table 2). Whether these varieties have a resistance mechanism whereby most hills get infested, but with the infestation limited to a few tillers needs further study. □

Table 2. Noncorrespondence of varietal infestation by GM as measured on hill and tiller basis.

Variety	Infected hill		Infected tiller		Variety	Infected hill		Infected tiller	
	%	Score	74	Score		%	Score	%	Score
20B	55	9	5	3	IRS4883-8-2-3	35	7	4	3
61759	30	7	5	3	IRS6382-112-1-3-2	15	9	4	3
Cisokan	25	7	5	3	IR56455-69-2-2-1	25	7	5	3
IR42	4	1	13	7	IR57311-99-1-3	40	7	4	3
IR19319-5-3-3-2-1	65	9	2	3	OR367-SP-11	25	7	4	3
IR33059-26-2-2	35	7	4	3	RP1125-1012-2-1-4	40	7	5	3
IR35353-94-2-1-3	45	7	3	3	RP1821-9-1-1-2	35	7	3	3
IR44426-35-3-3-2	24	7	5	3	RP2069-16-9-5	45	7	5	3
IR49631-B-B-30-1	26	7	5	3	RP2107-8-12	35	7	5	3
IR51075-29-1-1-2-1	4	1	14	7					

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Breeding for cold tolerance at reproductive phase in the high hills of Nepal

B. R. Shapit (present address: Centre For Arid Zone Studies, University College of North Wales, Thoday Building, Bangor, Gwynedd LL57 2UW, Wales, UK), Lumle Regional Agricultural Research Centre (LRARC), P.O. Box No. 1, Kaski, Pokhara; and K. P. Shrestha, Central Division of Plant Breeding and Biotechnology, National Agricultural Research Centre, Khumaltar, Nepal

Injury caused by low temperature is a major constraint to improving rice production in the high hills of Nepal. Most cold-tolerant materials fail to set grains because minimum air temperatures (<15°C) are low from booting (Aug on) to maturity (Table 1).

We are now screening introduced and segregating materials in the field at four altitudes (1,250 m, 1,400 m, 1,675 m, and 2,000 m asl). At 2,000 m in Chhomro, almost all internationally known cold-tolerant exotic and indigenous varieties were sterile.

We crossed indigenous cold-tolerant varieties Chomrong, Dhunge dhan, and Jumli Marshi with exotic cold-tolerant varieties Fuji 102, Akiyudaka, K332, and NR10157-2B-2, and with high-yielding varieties IR36 and NR10078-100-3-3. Seeds of F₁ generations grown at Khumaltar (1,350m) were divided into two lots for testing at 1,400-m and 2,000 m.

Table 1. Average air and water temperatures (°C) at Lumle (1,400 m) and Chhomro (2,000 m) testing sites of the Lumle Regional Agricultural Research Centre, Nepal, 1990.^a

Month	Lumle			Chhomro		
	Air		Water	Air		Water
	Max	Min		Max	Min	
May	23.3	14.6	NR	24.4	12.0	NR
Jun	24.7	17.1	NR	24.8	11.4	NR
Jul	24.0	17.6	22.0	23.4	15.3	21.2
Aug	23.7	17.4	20.8	24.4	14.7	20.8
Sep	23.5	16.6	19.6	22.3	14.2	NR
Oct	21.1	12.2	17.8	19.9	10.0	NR
Nov	19.3	11.4	NR	17.5	8.3	NR
Mean	22.8	15.3	20.1	22.4	12.3	21.0

^aNR = not recorded.

Results with segregating materials from crosses between Chhomrong and exotic materials and from crosses of cold-tolerant K332 with moderately cold-tolerant Nepalese breeding line NR10157-2B-2 were promising (Table 2).

The crosses of indigenous cold-tolerant Chhomrong with exotic cold-tolerant Fuji

102 and with susceptible IR36 both set grain at the Chhomro site; progenies of other cold-tolerant materials (except K332/NR10157-2B-2) did not set grain. At 1,400 m in Lumle, most of the F₂ population produced grain. Some promising plants were selected from all crosses.

At Chhomro, segregation for cold tolerance at anthesis in Fuji 102/Chhomrong and K332/NR10157-2B-2 fitted a simple inheritance ratio of 3:1. This suggests that cold tolerance at anthesis in those crosses could be governed by a single dominant gene.

At Chhomro, progenies of K332 and NR10157-2B-2 produced several plants with good seed set, while the individual parents failed to produce grain. This suggests that inheritance of cold tolerance for spikelet fertility can be accumulated by crossing moderately cold-tolerant parents.

The genetics of cold tolerance at anthesis in Chhomrong and other promising indigenous varieties is being studied at Lumle. □

Table 2. Cold tolerance^a of selected crosses at Lumle (1,400 m) and Chhomro (2,000 m), Nepal, 1990.

Cross	Lumle ^b		Chhomro ^c	
	Resistant (no.)	Resistant ^d (no.)	Susceptible ^e (no.)	
Fuji 102/Chhomrong	7	14	26	
Fuji 102/Dhunge dhan	6	0	40	
NR10078-100-3-3/Jumli Marshi	4	0	40	
Akiyudaka/Dhunge dhan	3	0	40	
Akiyudaka/Jumli Marshi	2	0	40	
IR36/Jumli Marshi	5	0	40	
IR36/Chhomrong	7	4	36	
K332/NR10157-2B-2	9	16	24	

^aMeasured in terms of failure to set grain or grain set at maturity. ^bChilling injury at reproductive phase. ^cChilling injury from booting to ripening stages. ^dResistant = plant sets grain. ^eSusceptible = plant fails to produce any grain.